

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF COMBINED NEUROPROTECTION IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19 DISEASE

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Abstract: This article discusses the clinical efficacy of combined neuroprotection in patients with COVID-19 disease. When detailing the results of testing on the MoCA scale, in general, the examined patients were dominated by changes in the executive function of drawing a broken line, optical-spatial disorders, and worsening of delayed word reproduction (hearing-speech memory). At the same time, auditory-verbal memory disorders were more often observed in patients with MG.

Keywords: clinical efficacy, neuroprotection, patients, COVID-19 disease, MoCA scale.

Introduction

During treatment, many patients experienced a transformation of severe hemiparesis and hemiplegia into mild hemiparesis and severe hemiparesis, respectively. "Increase in improvement" - Δ in subgroups MG-1 and CG-1 was greater compared to subgroups MG-2 and CG-2, respectively, and had significant differences (v.3).

Pathological reflexes were characteristic of most of the examined patients: in 46 (95.8%) in MG-1, in 29 (96.7%) in MG-2, in 20 (86.9%) in CG-1 and in 18 (85.7%) in CG-2. After treatment, the percentage of patients with pathological reflexes decreased in MG-1 by 25.0%, in MG-2 by 13.3%, in CG-1 by 17.4%, in CG-2 by 14.3%. With significant differences between subgroups MG-1 and MG-2 and CG-1 and CG-2.

The main findings and results

Among other focal neurological symptoms in the examined patients, there were violations of sensitivity on the side opposite to the affected hemisphere - in 42 (87.5%) in MG-1, in 24 (80.0%) in MG-2, in 19 (82.6%) in CG-1 and in 17 (81.0%) in CG-2. In the dynamics against the background of treatment, there was an improvement in symptoms (hemihypesthesia regressed) by 16.7% in MG-1, by 13.3% in MG-2, by 13.0% in CG-1 and by 4.5% in CG-1. 2. Significantly good regression of hemihypesia was observed in subgroups with the addition of neuroprotective therapy (v.3). Meningeal symptoms were not detected in patients.

Dysfunction of the pelvic organs was expressed in urination disorders in the form of urinary incontinence of central origin, stool retention and was observed in 7 (14.6%) in MG-1, in 4 (13.3%) in MG-2, in 3 (20, 8%) in CG-1 and 5 (23.8%) in CG-2. Improvement of this symptomatology in MG-1 was observed by 12.5%, in MG-2 by 13.0%, in CG-1 by 9.5%. There were no significant differences in this category of symptoms.

Cortical speech disorders were observed in 10 (20.8%) in MG-1, in 5 (10.4%) in MG-2, in 4 (17.4%) in CG-1 and in 5 (23.8%) in CG-2. On the background of treatment, a good dynamics was observed in the subgroups MG-1 and CG-2 ($p < 0.05$).

According to the research results, it can be noted that the transferred COVID-19 slowed down the recovery of impaired functions, which is especially evident in MG-2 compared to CG-2, despite standard therapy and exercise therapy. During treatment with the addition of neuroprotective therapy, there was an improvement in symptoms in both groups with significant differences in many symptoms.

Здесь и далее: Примечание: достоверность различий * - $p < 0,05$; ** - $p < 0,005$.

Figure 1. Dynamics of indicators on the Rankin scale over the observation period.

According to the Rankin scale in MG-1 and MG-2 there were initially high scores -4.6+1.2 and 4.5+1.1 points, respectively. During treatment, the scores significantly decreased to 2.9+0.2 and 3.1+0.5, respectively. Prior to treatment in the acute period, the Rankin scores in CG-1 and CG-2 were significantly lower compared to MG-1 and MG-2. But after treatment, positive dynamics was also observed in these subgroups, and based on Figure 1, in groups where patients

received additional neuroprotective therapy, a rapid and significant regression of symptoms was observed.

According to the NIHSS scale used to determine the level of neurological deficit in MG-1 and MG-2, the following indicators were initially -23.52 and 23.68 points, respectively. In the dynamics against the background of treatment, the indicators improved, this was especially noticeable in the MG-1 subgroup ($p < 0.005$) - 16.47 and 17.61, respectively. In subgroups CG-1 and CG-2, the NIHSS scores were 18.23 and 18.59 points, respectively, after rehabilitation measures - 14.28 and 15.12 points, respectively. In these subgroups, it is also noticeable that patients on the background of neuroprotection showed better results on the NIHSS scale.

Figure 2. Dynamics of changes in indicators on a scale over the observation period.

According to the MoCA scale in the MG-1 mental status assessment conducted after treatment, the average value of the indicator is 20.3 ± 1.8 points, which corresponds to moderate cognitive impairment and is (20.5 ± 2.17) (Fig. 3) . When ranking the results of the MoCA scale for assessing the mental status in MG-1, the test result significantly improved - 24.6 ± 1.3 points ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, the results of the study of indicators of neurological status and cognitive sphere showed that patients with hemispheric ischemic stroke who underwent COVID-19 have more pronounced neurological symptoms and cognitive deficits. Three months after treatment, patients with hemispheric ischemic stroke who received neuroprotective therapy showed a significant trend towards a decrease in cognitive deficit in patients in the recovery period of an ischemic stroke.

Conclusion

In the subgroups of patients who were on standard therapy, a slower dynamics of recovery of the neurological status and cognitive sphere was observed. Probably, such a not so pronounced picture of recovery was associated with insufficient standard treatment for this category of patients, due to the aggravation of the transferred COVID-19.

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